

Large-scale multiactor training and mentorship programme to ASSist people with physical impairments in energy povERTy

D2.3 – Energy Disability Policy Tracker

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1. Report information

Purpose of the Report	This report accompanies the Online Energy Disability Policy Tracker tool, providing a concise explanation of the tool's purpose, structure, and functionalities. It summarises the methodology, data sources and co-creation process used to develop the tracker, and describes how the tool supports the evaluation of energy poverty and disability-related measures in ASSERT's five pilot countries.
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2. ABOUT ASSERT

The ASSERT project is a European initiative funded under the LIFE23-CET-ENERPOV framework, which will address the critical issue of energy poverty, particularly among people with physically disabilities.

The project goal is three-fold:

1. Ensure that policy makers at all levels of administrations, as well as energy practitioners and advisors, receive training on energy issues, including energy poverty, while fully accounting for the multidimensional nature of energy poverty and the broader context of clean energy transition.
2. Roll-out programmes to train front line workers on energy poverty and green energy solutions. Front-line workers to be trained include health and social care workers or other professionals who can help identify households inhabited by people with disabilities and experiencing energy poverty and provide them with advice and information on solutions to reduce energy consumption and access more affordable and innovative sources.
3. Offer targeted training courses for vulnerable households, including those with low digital skills. Such courses should enhance the energy and digital literacy awareness of households affected by energy poverty, enable them to better control their energy bills and actively participate in the clean and just energy transition.

ASSERT will focus on people with physical disabilities who often have higher energy needs and lower incomes and therefore are more susceptible to energy poverty and its effects. Addressing their needs can interrupt the vicious circle of aggravating health conditions because of unhealthy household conditions related to experiencing energy poverty.

The project will deliver an integrated target-specific training and mentorship programme for local policymakers and intermediaries and will equip them with essential skills and knowledge and support to implement sustainable energy solutions, while integrating energy poverty considerations into broader policy frameworks.

3. ASSERT consortium

Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
AISFOR SRL	AISFOR SRL	IT
RETE ASSIST - ETS	RETE ASSIST - ETS	IT
ENERCOOP	ENERCOOP	FR
ASOCIACION ECOSERVEIS	ECOSERVEIS	ES
CITIZEN CROSSROADS	CCR	EL
ENERGEIAKO GRAFEIO KYPROU	CEA	CY
CLIMATE ALLIANCE - KLIMA-BUENDNIS - ALIANZA DEL CLIMA e.V.	CLIMATE ALLIANCE	DE
EUROPEAN NETWORK ON INDEPENDENT LIVING BRUSSELS OFFICE	ENIL	BE
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS	NTUA	EL
INSTITUTE FOR EUROPEAN ENERGY AND CLIMATE POLICY STICHTING	IEECP	NL
ACCADEMIA EUROPEA DI BOLZANO	Eurac	IT

Table of Contents

Contents

1. Report information	2
2. ABOUT ASSERT	3
3. ASSERT consortium	4
4. Executive summary	6
1. Introduction	7
2. Methodology & Data Sources	8
3. Platform Architecture & Functionalities	9
4. Accessibility and GDPR	14
5. Expected Impact	15
6. Conclusion	16

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Landing Page of the Tracker.....	9
Figure 2: Interactive Map of Participating Countries.....	10
Figure 3: AIY Accessibility Menu.....	11
Figure 4: Country Page – Example: Greece.....	11
Figure 5: Local Pilot Policies – Example from Greece.....	12
Figure 6: Policy Pop-Up Window – Full Policy Details.....	13

4.Executive summary

This document accompanies the [Online Energy Disability Policy Tracker](#), which provides an accessible, web-based platform for exploring and mapping national and local policies relating to energy poverty mitigation and providing support to people with disabilities in the ASSERT pilot countries of Italy, Cyprus, Greece, France, and Spain. The report briefly outlines the structure of the tool, the methodology followed to collect the relevant information, and the main functionalities that guide users through the online platform. The tracker consolidates information into a consistent format, supporting comparison across countries and helping municipalities and stakeholders strengthen their policy actions.

1. Introduction

This document accompanies the Online Energy Disability Policy Tracker, one of the tools developed within the ASSERT project. This report aims to provide a brief explanation of the tool structure and content, outlining how the tracker is organised and how a user can navigate it. The following sections summarise the methodology and the core functionalities of the tool.

The tracker was developed to consolidate national and local policies that relate to energy poverty mitigation and provide support to people with disabilities in a single, accessible environment. Its purpose is to facilitate quick access to structured information, support the identification of relevant measures in the ASSERT pilot countries and municipalities, and provide a clear overview of the existing policy landscape at a national and local level. By organising policies in a consistent format across the pilot countries, the tool enables potential beneficiaries with physical disabilities and municipal employees or social workers to discover available supporting policies within their municipality and at a national level, while also inspiring other local and regional authorities across Europe to adopt relevant best practices.

To build this consolidated resource, information on national and local measures across Italy, Cyprus, Greece, France, and Spain was collected, organised and harmonised into a unified format. The tracker integrates both energy-poverty-related measures and financial support schemes for persons with disabilities, ensuring that users can explore policies across both domains in a coherent and user-friendly way. The tool has been further refined through co-creation activities and feedback from stakeholders and potential users, ensuring that its structure and content respond to real needs.

2. Methodology & Data Sources

The tracker is based on policy information collected from the five ASSERT pilot countries (Italy, Cyprus, Greece, France, and Spain) through structured desk research. This included a desk-based review for the national legislation and delving into the specific policies at a municipal level for the municipalities involved. The documentation of local policies was further supported by interactions and interviews with municipalities carried out within the project's mentorship framework. All identified measures were gathered and organised using a common template to ensure consistency across countries and comparability between national and local levels.

3. Platform Architecture & Functionalities

This section provides a brief, user-oriented overview of how to navigate and use the Energy Disability Policy Tracker.

The Tracker is available here: <https://edpt.assert.epu.ntua.gr/> and can also be accessed through the ASSERT website: <https://assert.aisforacademy.eu/>.

The platform integrates the EU flag and the official funding acknowledgement statement, fully complying with the visibility and communication rules of the Grant Agreement.

The walkthrough below follows the typical user flow, starting from the landing page and moving through the main features of the platform.

Figure 1: Landing Page of the Tracker

Participating Countries

Click on a highlighted country on the map to view its financial aid resources

Figure 2: Interactive Map of Participating Countries

The landing page introduces the purpose of the tool and provides direct access to information from all participating countries. Users can access more information about a country by clicking on the highlighted country on the map or by using the “Countries” option in the top navigation bar. The main navigation options (Home, Countries, About Us, FAQ and Contact) are available in the top menu bar, together with the AIY accessibility button. This page provides an overview of the tool and acts as the starting point for exploring national and local policies.

The interactive map highlights the five ASSERT pilot countries. By selecting Greece, Cyprus, Italy, Spain or France, users are taken to the country-specific page where national and local policies are displayed. This feature allows quick access without navigating through menus.

Figure 3: A11Y Accessibility Menu

The A11Y button provides quick accessibility options. Users can activate large text, reduce motion, increase text spacing or enable grayscale mode. These adjustments improve readability and usability for people with visual, cognitive or sensory difficulties and were introduced following feedback from several interactive workshops that took place with potential users.

Figure 4: Country Page – Example: Greece

Each country page is organised into two main sections: *Energy Poverty Mitigation Policies* and *Policies Supporting People with Disabilities*. Users can switch between

National and ASSERT Pilots using the tabs at the top of each category. Policy cards provide a brief description of each policy, eligibility information, and application guidance, with the option to view more details through the “More Information” button.

Energy Poverty mitigation Policies

National **ASSERT Pilots**

Filter by Municipality: All Municipalities

Municipal Energy Support in Veria

One-off financial support for energy bills after assessment, occasional mediation for reconnection within national policy, and recognition of medical equipment energy needs. The municipality also coordinates across support structures and provides documentation to reconnect vulnerable groups (e.g., PwD).

Eligibility: Vulnerable households and individuals assessed by the Office of Social Affairs and Policy (e.g., PwD, low-income).

How to apply: Through the Office of Social Affairs and Policy, following municipal procedures.

[More Information](#) Veria

Municipal Energy Assistance in Komotini

Includes provision of fuel and heating oil after social assessment, support for energy bill reductions and exemptions (e.g., KOT), fee reductions for low-income or disabled residents, access to air-conditioned/heated municipal spaces, and emergency outreach during extreme weather.

Eligibility: Low-income households and residents with disabilities, assessed through the Social Protection Department.

How to apply: Applications via the Social Protection Department, Community Center, or Social Services of the Municipality.

[More Information](#) Komotini

Municipal Energy Initiatives in Thermaikos

Relies mainly on national programs (e.g., social tariffs), local data collection through food banks and community support, and participation in national energy-saving consultations.

Eligibility: Low-income households and vulnerable groups supported via national and municipal schemes.

How to apply: Through the Municipal Youth Council, Community Centre, or by applying to relevant national programs.

[More Information](#) Thermaikos

Municipal Energy Programs in Kifisia

Includes the EU Urban Initiative positive-energy school building project, applications to national programs ('Phoebus', 'Athena', 'Electra'), and plans to relaunch an energy community for vulnerable groups.

Eligibility: Schools, low-income households, and vulnerable residents within Kifisia municipality.

How to apply: Applications via the Strategic Planning Office, Kifisia Development Organisation, or Social Services Department.

[More Information](#) Kifisia

Figure 5: Local Pilot Policies – Example from Greece

Local-level policies from the ASSERT pilot municipalities are displayed under the “ASSERT Pilots” tab for both energy poverty measures and disability-related support schemes. A dropdown menu allows filtering by municipality. This structure enables users to explore measures implemented at the local level, compare approaches across municipalities and understand how national frameworks are adapted and applied in local contexts.

Energy Solidarity Benefit
×

Program Overview

The Energy Solidarity Benefit (Κοινωνικό Τιμολόγιο Ηλεκτρισμού) is a comprehensive financial support program designed to help low-income households manage their electricity costs during challenging economic times. This benefit provides direct financial assistance to cover a significant portion of electricity bills for eligible households.

Detailed Eligibility Requirements

To qualify for this benefit, applicants must meet the following criteria:

- Annual household income below €12,000 for single-person households
- Annual household income below €18,000 for two-person households
- Additional €3,000 allowance for each dependent child
- Greek citizenship or legal residence status
- Must be the primary account holder of the electricity bill

Benefits Included

- Monthly discount of up to 70% on electricity bills
- Protection from power disconnection
- Retroactive application for up to 12 months
- Automatic renewal if eligibility criteria continue to be met

Required Documents

- Income tax return (E1 form)
- Electricity bill
- Identity card or passport
- AMKA (Social Security Number)
- Bank account details for direct deposit

How to Apply

The application process involves several steps: First, gather all required documents listed above. Then, visit your nearest KEP (Citizen Service Center) with original documents and copies. Alternatively, apply online through gov.gr using your TaxisNet credentials. The application is reviewed within 30 days, and if approved, the benefit is applied retroactively from the application date.

Application Timeline

Applications are processed within 30 business days. Benefits are applied immediately upon approval and continue for 12 months with automatic renewal if eligibility is maintained.

Contact Information

Phone: +30 210 123 4567
 Email: energyaid@gov.gr
 Office: Ministry of Environment and Energy, Social Policy Department

[Visit Official Website](#)

Close

Figure 6: Policy Pop-Up Window – Full Policy Details

The pop-up window in each policy provides the complete set of information for each policy in a structured, scrollable format. The upper section presents the programme overview, detailed eligibility requirements and the benefits offered. The lower section includes the required documents for application, instructions on how to apply, the expected processing timeline, the contact details of the responsible authority, together with a direct link to the official website. This consolidated view enables users to access all essential information about a policy without leaving the country page.

4. Accessibility and GDPR

This tool utilizes Google Analytics (GA4) to collect anonymized usage statistics for the purpose of improving user experience. No personally identifiable information (PII) is stored, and IP addresses are automatically excluded from logs. In compliance with GDPR, analytics scripts are disabled by default. Tracking activates only if the user explicitly grants permission via the consent banner. Users may modify or withdraw consent at any time via the 'Cookie Settings' interface.

The tool will remain available and updated throughout the ASSERT project and be integrated into the project website, allowing updates to national and local policy information during its duration. After the project ends, NTUA will be responsible for the sustainability of the tool.

5. Expected Impact

The Energy Disability Policy Tracker contributes to a clearer understanding of available support measures related to energy poverty and disability, offering practical value to a wide range of users. Its benefits extend across three key user groups:

- Empowering individuals facing energy poverty or people with disabilities. The tracker helps potential beneficiaries easily access national policies that may support them. For residents within the ASSERT pilot municipalities, local policies are also available, giving users a clear overview of services, rights, and programmes they can rely on.
- Supporting municipal employees in social and energy services. The tool acts as a one-stop-shop of information, enabling staff to quickly identify available measures and better assist citizens. This improves service delivery, reduces information gaps, and strengthens the municipality's ability to respond to local needs.
- Inspiring municipalities beyond the ASSERT project. Other local authority representatives can explore good practices implemented across Europe. The tracker enables comparison, mutual learning, and the uptake of effective policy approaches, helping them enhance their own strategies to address energy poverty and support persons with disabilities.

6. Conclusion

The Energy Disability Policy Tracker offers a simple and accessible way to navigate energy poverty and disability-related policies within the ASSERT pilot countries. Its structured format and ease of use support informed policy development and promote knowledge sharing. The tool will continue to be updated during the project to reflect new information and maintain its relevance.

Assert Consortium

PROJECT FACTS

Start date: 01/10/2024 **Duration:** 36M **Call:** LIFE-2023-CET **Coordinator:** AISFOR SRL (AISFOR)